

Synthesis of Some 2-Thenoyl-, 5-Bromo-2-thenoyl- and 5-Nitro-2-thenoylamino Acid Derivatives and their Antimicrobial Activity

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The synthesis of 2-thenoyl-, 5-bromo-2-thenoyl- and 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-XXVI) and the corresponding hydrazides (XXVII-XLVII) and some dipeptide derivatives (XLVIII-LXVI) is described. Some of the 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid methyl ester derivatives, (XIX-XXI and XXIII-XXV), the hydrazides (XLV and XLVI), the dipeptides (LXI-LXIV) and 5-bromo-2-thenoyl-L-tyr-N₂H, (XL) and 2-thenoyl-L-val-OMe (VII) and 2-thenoyl-DL-ala-gly-OMe (L) are found to be active against a number of microorganisms.

MANY substituted thiophenes exhibit bacteriostatic, antihistaminic, anaesthetic, antispasmodic, hypnotic, antiviral, anticonvulsant and other pharmacological activities¹⁻⁹. Later, the synthesis of new furan- and thiophene-2-CO-amino acids was reported and the compounds were found to possess some biological activities¹⁰⁻¹². However, the effect of variation of the functional groups and substitution in both the thiophene and amino acid moieties on the biological and pharmacological activities has not been studied yet.

The present investigation involves the synthesis of some 2-thenoyl-, 5-bromo-2-thenoyl- and 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters and their corresponding hydrazides and dipeptide derivatives (IV-LXVI) and studies of their microbiological activities.

2-Thenoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-X), 5-bromo-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (XI-XVIII) and 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXVI) were readily prepared by the reaction of 2-thenoyl chloride (I)¹³ or 5-bromo-2-thenoyl chloride (II)¹⁴ or 5-nitro-2-thenoyl chloride (III)¹⁵ with appropriate amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride in methylene chloride-triethylamine medium. The time required for completion of the reactions (3-4 hr) was monitored by tlc. Methylene chloride was found to be the most proper solvent for such coupling reactions. When ether, benzene, THF, dioxane or DMF were used instead of methylene chloride, the products IV-XXVI were obtained in very poor (10-30%) yields and some by-products were isolated. Compounds IV-XXVI were chromatographically homogeneous and did not respond to ninhydrin reaction. Complete acid hydrolysis of IV for 24 hr afforded glycine. The ir spectrum of IV in KBr showed characteristic bands at 3340, 3060 (NH); 1760 ($\nu_{C=O}$); 1640, 1560, 1360 (amide I, II and III);

1760, 1480, 1360 and 1050 (COOCH_3); 3020, 1420, 1340, 1180, 1050, 890 and 765 cm^{-1} (thiophene and amino acid moieties) confirming its structure. The uv spectrum of IV in ethanol revealed the expected maxima of the thiophene moiety at λ_{max} ($\log \epsilon$) 280 nm (3.95); 227 nm (3.83) and 208 nm (3.74). Analogous peaks were observed in the ir and uv spectra of other compounds concordant with their structures.

The hydrazides XXVII-XLVII were prepared by treatment of the corresponding methyl esters IV-XXVI with hydrazine hydrate in methanol. The products were purified by repeated recrystallization.

2-Thenoyl dipeptide methyl esters (XLVIII-LV), 5-bromo-2-thenoyldipeptide methyl esters (LVI-LXI) and 5-nitro-2-thenoyldipeptide methyl esters (LXII-LXVI) were prepared via the azide method. The hydrazides XXVII-XLVII were converted into the corresponding azides which on coupling with the amino acid esters furnished the dipeptides XLVIII-LXVI which were isolated and purified in the usual manner¹⁶. Structures of XLVIII-LXVI were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses, chromatographic studies, spot tests and ir and uv spectra.

(Compounds IV-LXVI)

Biological screening results: The antimicrobial activity of compounds IV-LXVI was tested using the hole plate method and filter paper disc method¹⁷⁻²⁰, and the results compared with the activity of the free acids of (I-III). 5-Nitro-2-thenoyl-gly-OMe (XIX) and 5-nitro-2-thenoyl-DL-ala-OMe (XX) were found to possess high antimicrobial activities against

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF VARIOUS 2-THENOYL-, 5-BROMO-2-THENOYL- AND 5-NITRO-2-THENOYLAMINO ACIDS AND DIPEPTIDE DERIVATIVES (IV-XLVI)

Compd. No.	R	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	R _f TLC	[α] _D ^{20*}
R' = H					
IV	-Gly-OMe	85	98-95	0.83	—
V	-DL-Ala-OMe	80	102-104	0.93	—
VI	-β-Ala-OMe	88	88-90	0.84	—
VII	-L-Val-OMe	89	77-79	0.89	-33.7 (c, 0.6, A)
VIII	-L-Leu-OMe	94	99-101	0.90	-19.6 (c, 0.6, A)
IX	-DL-Phe-OMe	96	111-113	0.83	—
X	-Ach-OMe	84	141-143	0.77	—
R' = Br					
XI	-Gly-OMe	90	96-98	0.78	—
XII	-DL-Ala-OMe	85	110-112	0.82	—
XIII	-β-Ala-OMe	82	100-102	0.81	—
XIV	-L-Val-OMe	81	93-95	0.86	- 5.6 (c, 0.6, B)
XV	-L-Leu-OMe	65	109-111	0.77	-10.5 (c, 0.2, B)
XVI	-DL-Phe-OMe	91	123-125	0.80	—
XVII	-L-Tyr-OMe	80	143-145	0.78	+7.5 (c, 0.4, C)
XVIII	-Ach-OMe	83	150-152	0.84	—
R' = NO₂					
XIX	-Gly-OMe	78	145-147	0.79	—
XX	-DL-Ala-OMe	88	123-125	0.85	—
XXI	-β-Ala-OMe	79	104-106	0.81	—
XXII	-L-Val-OMe	89	200-202	0.88	- 12.5 (c, 0.3, C)
XXIII	-L-Leu-OMe	75	98-100	0.76	+15 (c, 0.6, C)
XXIV	-DL-Phe-OMe	89	141-143	0.73	—
XXV	-L-Tyr-OMe	70	177-179	0.77	- 11.5 (c, 0.3, B)
XXVI	-Ach-OMe	71	143-145	0.83	—
R' = H					
XXVII	-Gly-N ₂ H ₅	92	178-180	0.73	—
XXVIII	-DL-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	87	168-170	0.75	—
XXIX	-β-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	78	228-230	0.72	—
XXX	-L-Val-N ₂ H ₅	86	184-186	0.78	- 6.9 (c, 1, B)
XXXI	-L-Leu-N ₂ H ₅	89	150-152	0.79	+16.9 (c, 0.6, B)
XXXII	-DL-Phe-N ₂ H ₅	95	188-190	0.80	—
XXXIII	-L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₅	83	231-233	0.73	+10 (c, 0.1, A)
R' = Br					
XXXIV	-Gly-N ₂ H ₅	84	228-230	0.60	—
XXXV	-DL-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	93	190-192	0.74	—
XXXVI	-β-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	86	178-180	0.79	—
XXXVII	-L-Val-N ₂ H ₅	83	189-191	0.78	- 11.6 (c, 0.6, B)
XXXVIII	-L-Leu-N ₂ H ₅	96	164-166	0.80	- 30.5 (c, 0.3, A)
XXXIX	-DL-Phe-N ₂ H ₅	87	222-224	0.75	—
XL	-L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₅	90	230-232	0.80	- 13.5 (c, 0.3, A)
R' = NO₂					
XLI	-Gly-N ₂ H ₅	93	201-203	0.81	—
XLII	-DL-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	88	149-151	0.74	—
XLIII	-β-Ala-N ₂ H ₅	80	156-158	0.63	—
XLIV	-L-Val-N ₂ H ₅	58	170-172	0.75	- 25.5 (c, 0.4, A)
XLV	-L-Leu-N ₂ H ₅	95	192-194	0.83	- 50 (c, 0.2, A)
XLVI	-DL-Phe-N ₂ H ₅	94	215-217	0.78	—
XLVII	-L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₅	78	220-222	0.74	- 7.5 (c, 0.2, A)
R' = H					
XLVIII	-Gly-Gly-OMe	62	119-121	0.70	—
XLIX	-Gly-L-leu-OMe	80	116-118	0.74	+ 30 (c, 1, A)
L	-DL-Ala-gly-OMe	72	154-156	0.79	—
LI	-L-Val-gly-OMe	75	165-167	0.76	- 8.5 (c, 2, A)
LII	-L-Leu-gly-OMe	78	170-172	0.73	+7.5 (c, 0.35, C)
LIII	-DL-Phe-gly-OMe	70	160-162	0.69	—
LIV	-DL-Phe-L-leu-OMe	59	135-137	0.70	+16.5 (c, 0.6, C)
LV	-L-Tyr-gly-OMe	58	99-101	0.72	+33.5 (c, 0.6, C)
R' = Br					
LVI	-Gly-L-leu-OMe	82	138-140	0.75	+ 20 (c, 0.5, A)
LVII	-DL-Ala-L-leu-OMe	66	142-144	0.63	- 40 (c, 1, D)
LVIII	-β-Ala-gly-OMe	69	160-162	0.78	—
LIX	-L-Leu-L-val-OMe	60	185-187	0.68	+10 (c, 0.5, D)
LX	-DL-Phe-DL-ala-OMe	73	182-184	0.77	—
LXI	-L-Tyr-gly-OMe	80	122-124	0.73	+16 (c, 0.6, D)

(Table 1 Contd.)

R' = NO ₂					
LXII	-Gly-L-leu-OMe	74	154-156	0.79	+5 (c, 2, B)
LXIII	-Gly-L-tyr-OMe	67	161-163	0.75	-27.5 (c, 0.9, D)
LXIV	-β-Ala-gly-OMe	70	196-198	0.72	—
LXV	-L-Leu-DL-phe-OMe	72	125-127	0.80	-16.5 (c, 0.6, A)
LXVI	-DL-Phe-L-leu-OMe	71	193-195	0.77	-30.5 (c, 1, B)

* $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ were measured in the solvents : (A) = DMF ; (B) = methylene chloride ; (C) = methanol ; (D) = chloroform.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

B. subtilis, *B. mycoides*, *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhosa* and *P. chrysogenum*. 5-Nitro-2-thenoyl-β-ala-OMe (XXI) and the corresponding -L-leu-OMe (XXIII), -L-tyr-OMe (XXV), -L-tyr-N₂H₃ (XLVII) and -gly-L-leu-OMe (LXII) derivatives showed antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis*, *B. mycoides* and *B. cereus*. 5-Nitro-2-thenoyl-L-leu-N₂H₃ (XLV) was found to be active against *B. subtilis*, *B. mycoides*, *B. cereus* and *P. chrysogenum*. 5-Nitro-2-thenoyl-gly-L-tyr-OMe (LXIII), 5-nitro-2-thenoyl-β-ala-gly-OMe (LXIV), 5-bromo-2-thenoyl-L-tyr-N₂H₃ (XL) and 2-thenoyl-L-val-OMe (VII) inhibited the growth of *B. mycoides* but did not inhibit the growth of *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*. 2-Thenoyl-DL-ala-gly-OMe (L) and 5-nitro-2-thenoyl-DL-phe-OMe (XXIV) produced antimicrobial effects and gave promising results against *B. subtilis* only. The remaining amino acid derivatives were found to be inactive against all the tested microorganisms. The present investigation revealed that substitution in the 5-position of the thenoyl moiety by nitro group in combination with amino acid esters, hydrazides and dipeptide residues gave 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid derivatives of high and specific biological properties. However, replacement of the 5-nitro group by 5-bromo group or its removal gave biologically inactive compounds. Other pharmacological studies are in progress.

Experimental

TLC (R_f) was taken on silica gel and developed with *n*-butanol-pyridine-acetic acid-water (30 : 20 : 6 : 24). *o*-Toluidine, benzidine, ninhydrin, silver nitrate and hydroxamate were used as spraying agents and for development (spot reactions). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ were measured using Carl Zeiss polarimeter, 1 dm tube at 20°. Ach = Aminocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid residue.

2-Thenoyl chloride (I), 5-bromo-2-thenoyl chloride (II) and 5-nitro-2-thenoyl chloride (III) : These were prepared according to the procedures described in the literature^{1, 2, 15}.

General procedure for synthesis of 2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-X), 5-bromo-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (XI-XVIII) and 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXVI) : 2-Thenoyl chloride (I) (1.46 g ; 0.01 mole) or 5-bromo-2-thenoyl chloride (II) (2.26 g ; 0.01 mole) or 5-nitro-2-thenoyl chloride (III) (1.92 g ; 0.01 mole)

dissolved anhyd. methylene chloride (25 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of the amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.012 mole) or aminocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (Ach) methyl ester^{2, 1} (0.012 mole) in methylene chloride (80 ml) containing triethylamine (4.5 ml). The reaction mixture was shaken for 30 min at room temperature and then refluxed for 3-4 hr, cooled to 0° and Et₃N.HCl filtered off and methylene chloride (30 ml) added. The mixture was washed with HCl (5%), H₂O, NaHCO₃ (5%), H₂O and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residual material recrystallized from benzene, ethanol, *n*-hexane, pet. ether or their mixtures. The products (IV-XXVI) were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with *o*-toluidine or benzidine) and had positive hydroxamate reaction.

General procedure for synthesis of 2-thenoylamino acid hydrazides (XXVII-XXXIII), 5-bromo-2-thenoylamino acid hydrazides (XXXIV-XL) and 5-nitro-2-thenoylamino acid hydrazides (XLI-XLVII) : To amino acid methyl ester (IV-XXVI) (0.01 mole) dissolved in methanol (100 ml), hydrazine hydrate (85%) (2.5 ml ; 0.05 mole) was added and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for 24 hr at 20°. The solvent was removed *in vacuo*, methanol added and re-evaporated several times and the crude product recrystallized from methanol or ethanol-water. The products (XXVII-XLVII) were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with *o*-toluidine) and gave positive silver nitrate reaction.

General procedure for synthesis of the dipeptide methyl esters (XLVIII-LXVI) : The amino acid hydrazide (XXVII-XLVII) (0.006 mole) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (8 ml), 5 N HCl (4 ml) and water (40 ml) and cooled to -5°. Sodium nitrite (0.53 g) in water (3 ml) was added and the mixture stirred for 5 min at -5°. The azide was extracted with ethyl acetate (50 ml) and the extract washed successively with H₂O, NaHCO₃ (5%) and H₂O and dried (Na₂SO₄). Compounds (XLVIII-LXVI) were prepared by the addition of ethyl acetate solution of the azide to a cooled (-5°) solution of the free amino acid methyl ester (prepared from 0.01 mole of the amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride and 0.9 ml triethylamine as described earlier^{1, 6}), and keeping the reaction mixture for 24 hr at 0° and for another 24 hr at room temperature. It was washed successively

with HCl (0.5 N), H₂O, NaHCO₃ (5%) and H₂O and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residual material recrystallized from benzene, ethanol or hexane. All dipeptides (XLVIII-LXVI) were found to be chromatographically homogeneous (detection with *o*-toluidine or benzidine) and gave positive hydroxamate reaction.

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